

The Effects of Perceived Web-Store Design Characteristics on Consumer's Affective States and Attitudes towards the Store

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Abstract

This study tests a model that proposes that design elements of the e-store create environmental atmospheric that induce certain emotional states in the consumer, which in turn affect his/her attitudes towards the store. The model is based on concepts from the human-computer interaction (HCI) literature and on the environmental psychology model of Mehrabian and Russell (1974). The atmospherics of the e-store is captured in our model by perceptions of two design dimensions: usability and aesthetics. The results support the model propositions by showing a significant effect of site atmospherics on the emotions experienced during the shopping episode and, consequently, on attitudes towards the store. The study contributes to the development of a richer and more adequate model of consumer behavior in online shopping, by merging HCI and marketing theories, and by taking into account the effects of design on emotions.

Keywords: Aesthetics, usability, design, human-computer interaction, store atmosphere, Web-store, E-retail, emotions

1. Introduction

A key issue in e-retail is the multi-disciplinary and complex nature of Web-store design. It includes the application of knowledge from diverse areas such as marketing, information technology, and human-computer interaction (HCI). The intriguing point about such an endeavor is that traditionally those fields have been occupied with a different set of goals and success criteria. Thus, for example, the field of marketing has been intensively involved in attempts to influence consumers' emotions through advertisements, and product and store design (e.g., Bloch, 1995; Kotler and Rath 1984). Considerations of efficient and accurate information processing, navigation, and task execution by customers are not of major concern here. On the contrary, some marketing techniques attempt to make the information processing or the shopping process even less efficient for various reasons (e.g., Russo, 1977; Schroeder, 2002).

The field of HCI, on the other hand, has traditionally been dedicated to the study and the practice of ease of use, and accurate and fast task execution while refraining from dealing with the affective aspects of the interaction in general and specifically with aesthetic issues (Norman, 2002; Tractinsky, 2004). Thus, the marriage of these contrasting disciplines in a new business model is challenging for both research and practice (Wind and Mahajan, 2002). Currently, there is very scarce research on the merger of marketing and HCI (Barwise et al., 2002; Vergo et al., 2003). Most of the existing attempts to study the design aspects of retail Web sites are not theory driven, and there is no robust theory to explain how Web site design affects emotions, consumers' beliefs, attitudes and willingness to purchase from a particular vendor.

Traditional and online retail have the same purpose: selling goods and services for profit. However, they differ considerably in terms of their qualitative characteristics, such as space, time, visual and social cues. One of the major drawbacks of electronic retailing over conventional retailing is that it is inherently less stimulating (Tractinsky and Rao, 2001). Considering this limitation and consumers' increased expectations from Web-based stores, e-retailers face major challenges in creating appropriate shopping environments. "Today, it begins with quality, usability, and reliability, and then moves way beyond. In the past, these design elements encompassed all a company needed. Now design must also include intimacy,

sensory delight, drama or surprise, genuine care for the customer, and a sense of shared values.” (Business Week online, 2005).

Atmospherics has been defined as “the conscious designing of space to create certain buyer effects, specifically, the designing of buying environments to produce specific emotional effects in the buyer that enhance purchase probability” (Kotler, 1973-1974). There is a considerable body of literature on factors that contribute to the atmosphere of traditional stores. However, only recently have researchers begun studying what influences the atmospherics of online stores. Eroglu et al. (2001) proposed that similar to traditional in-store stimuli, online atmospheric cues (e.g., colors, graphics, layout, and design) can provide information about the retailer (e.g., the quality or type of retailer, the target audience of the retailer). They can also influence shoppers' responses during the site visit. However, the questions of which design factors affect the atmosphere of online stores and how these effects translate to consumers' emotions and behavior remain open.

This study posits that the atmospherics of a Web-based store can be captured by HCI design factors, and that key emotional reactions and attitudes towards the store can be captured by an environmental psychology model (Mehrabian and Russell, 1974). We present the research model and hypotheses in the next section. Section 3 describes the research method. Section 4 presents the results, which are discussed in Section 5.

2. Research Model and Hypotheses

Mehrabian and Russell's (1974) model suggests that environmental stimuli are perceived in terms of their affective qualities and affect the perceiver's emotional state. Emotional states can be reduced into a set of basic underlying dimensions. Mehrabian and Russell (1974) proposed three such bipolar dimensions, abbreviated PAD: Pleasure, Arousal (also referred to in the literature as activation), and Dominance (or perceived control). Subsequently, the person's emotional state influences her attitudes towards the environment, framed as "approach avoidance" response (see Figure 1). The PAD model and its derivatives have been used extensively in the study of physical retail environments (e.g. Donovan and Rossiter, 1982; Bellizzi and Hite, 1992; Donovan et al., 1994). Recent empirical research has demonstrated that online shopping environments can also evoke emotional responses in consumers (Machleit and Eroglu 2000, Eroglu et al. 2005).

Figure 1: The Mehrabian-Russell model of environmental influence

Recently, HCI researchers have joined marketing scholars in acknowledging the importance of aesthetics (Tractinsky, 2004) and emotions (e.g., Zhang and Li, 2005). The research framework suggested here integrates these two aspects by viewing aesthetics as an antecedent to emotion. The PAD model has been used very sparsely in the context of online shopping (Eroglu et al., 2003; Fiore et al., 2005; Mummalaneni, 2005). While these studies have demonstrated to various degrees the applicability of the model to the online environment, the relations between design attributes of online stores and consumers affective states remain largely unexplored.

The research framework, depicted in Figure 2, suggests that perceptions of the e-retail environment (as captured by the site's usability and aesthetics) induce certain emotional states (PAD) in the consumer, which in turn affect his/her attitudes toward the store. The model's constructs and hypothesized relationships are described below.

Figure 2: The Research Model

2.1. Environment – Emotions Relationships

The environment of the proposed model is comprised of two salient aspects of the online store: its usability and aesthetics. Based on Lavie and Tractinsky (2004), the aesthetic aspect can be further divided into two sub-dimensions: classical aesthetics and expressive aesthetics. The classical aesthetics sub-dimension emphasizes orderly and clear design; Expressive aesthetics represent qualities that go beyond the classical principles and that stress the designer's creativity and expressive power (Lavie and Tractinsky, 2004).

In general, we expect both aesthetic dimensions to positively correlate with the emotional state of pleasure, since pleasure is regarded as a prominent emotion accompanying the aesthetic experience (e.g. Sheppard, 1987; Coates, 2003). This premise is based not only on philosophical, linguistic, or theoretical grounds, but also on empirical evidence (e.g. Lavie and Tractinsky, 2004; Gannon, 2005).

Thus, we hypothesize:

H1: Sites perceived by users as having higher levels of classical aesthetics induce higher levels of pleasure.

H2: Sites perceived by users as having higher levels of expressive aesthetics induce higher levels of pleasure.

Due to its emphasis on novel and creative stimuli, expressive aesthetics is expected to correlate positively with arousal (e.g., Berlyne, 1971). Classical aesthetics, on the other hand, adhere to familiar and accepted notions of design, has a calming effect on the senses.

Consequently, we derive the following hypotheses:

H3: Sites perceived by users as having higher levels of expressive aesthetics induce higher levels of arousal.

H4: Sites perceived by users as having higher levels of classical aesthetics induce lower levels of arousal.

The usability of a site is expected to correlate positively with perceptions of dominance. The HCI literature has long emphasized the importance of allowing the user to be in control of the technological environment (e.g., Brown, 1986; Shneiderman, 1998) and the role of usability in achieving such control. Users' perceptions of control over the interaction and of the likelihood of achieving their goals are correlated with their affective states (Brave and Nass, 2003). In addition, smoother interactions facilitated by better usability are likely to increase pleasure, whereas lower levels of usability increase frustration (Brave and Nass, 2003) and thus reduce pleasure. Hence, we hypothesize that usability effects on emotions will be as follows:

H5: Sites perceived by users as more usable will increase feelings of dominance.

H6: Sites perceived by users as more usable will induce higher levels of pleasure.

Finally, previous studies have found that perceptions of systems' usability and aesthetics might be related (Tractinsky et al., 2000; Lindgaard and Dudek, 2003). This is especially the case concerning the relations between usability and classical aesthetics (Lavie and Tractinsky, 2004). Thus, positive association between the aesthetics factors and usability is also expected.

H7: There will be positive association between users' perceptions of sites' perceived usability and classical aesthetics

2.2. Emotions – Approach/Avoidance Relationships

We expect that consumers who are more pleased and who feel more in control of their environment will exhibit greater approach, rather than avoidance, tendencies. For example, Koufaris et al. (2002) findings show that perceived control and shopping enjoyment can increase the intention of new Web customers to return. The relations between arousal and approach/avoidance may be more complicated. Firstly, they may reflect the inverted U-shaped relations often observed between arousal and other attitudinal or behavioral measures (e.g., Berlyne 1971). Secondly, these relations may be contingent upon the nature of the shopping sites and products.

Thus, our hypotheses regarding the relationships with approach/avoidance concentrate only on the effects of pleasure and dominance.

H8: Higher levels of pleasure will increase users' approach response.

H9: Higher levels of dominance will increase users' approach response.

3. Method

3.1. Preliminary Qualitative Study

We conducted a preliminary qualitative study to gauge the adequacy of the theoretical framework constructs and to examine if the model's environmental constructs can influence emotional states. The study included three semi-structured interviews, which were tape recorded and transcribed.

Based on reactions, thoughts and opinions regarding three e-commerce sites, the data included distinct references to design aspects of the sites as well as a rich set of emotions. It appears that the aesthetic and the usability aspects of the sites' design have produced emotion through a non-mediated, direct impact on the senses. The aesthetics of the artifact was sensed as pleasant, arousing, boring, or annoying, results comparable to Rafaeli and Vilnai-Yavetz (2004). The sites' usability induced emotions such as pleasure and controllability. Thus, albeit initial and limited, the findings supported the notion of usability and aesthetic as design dimensions of e-commerce sites that induce atmospheric perceptions. The results also support the idea of direct relation between those design dimensions and the users' emotional states.

3.2. Main Study

Following the preliminary study, we conducted the main study, which tested the model, including the relations between the aesthetics and usability of a site, the emotions it evokes and the approach/avoidance response it produces.

Sample. Sixty-one students (about 73% males) participated in the study for class credit. The average age of the participants was 25.4.

Measures. Participants filled a questionnaire that included multiple-item scales for measuring the model's variables: The environment's variables, which include Classical Aesthetics, Expressive Aesthetics, and Usability; The emotional states variables: Pleasure, Arousal and Dominance; and Approach/Avoidance response operationalized as attitudes towards the sites. We adopted the items for the aesthetics and usability scales from Lavie and Tractinsky (2004). Items for the emotional states scales were adopted from Mehrabian and Russell (1974) and were slightly modified to fit the e-retail context. The items for the approach-avoidance scale were adopted from Donovan and Rossiter (1982). All scales consisted of seven-point Likert-type items ranging from (1) “strongly disagree” to (7) “strongly agree”.

Procedure. The participants were randomly assigned to one of the five retail domains (flowers, music CDs, cars, furniture or house painting). In each domain, participants visited three different sites, performing the task of ostensibly purchasing an item via the site. After visiting each site, they completed the questionnaire, based upon their impression of that site.

4. Results

We conducted an exploratory factor analysis to assess the discriminant validity of the model's variables. We followed the literature's recommendations for conducting such studies (e.g., Fabrigar et al., 1999; Conway and Huffcutt, 2003). We used a common factor model (Maximum Likelihood) as the factor extraction method and an oblique factor rotation method. The number of factors for extraction was predetermined to seven based on the number of the constructs in the model.

In essence, all items were loaded on their respective factors with two exceptions. Firstly, the Arousal items were loaded on two distinct factors - negative and positive – instead of on one bipolar factor. This result reflects the ambiguity of the Arousal construct, which has been

noted before in the marketing domain (Donovan et al., 1994), including its potential bi-dimensionality (Brenngman and Geuens, 2003; Smith and Apter, 1975). Secondly, two of the Dominance items were loaded on the Usability factor. Consequently, we rerun the factor analysis without these two items, and specified eight factors for extraction instead of seven factors in order to account for the emergence of two Arousal factors. Appendix 1 displays the rotated pattern matrix of the revised factor analysis. As can be seen from this table and from the reliabilities reported in Table 1, all variables are distinct, unidimensional and reliable.

Descriptive statistics, reliabilities and intercorrelations of the model's variables are provided in Table 1. The table indicates that, on average, the sites were perceived as about average in terms of their aesthetics qualities and above average in terms of usability. Emotional states ranged from low arousal (both negative and positive), somewhat below average pleasure and above average feelings of dominance. Overall attitudes towards the sites were below average, indicating a slight tendency to avoid, rather than approach them.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics, Cronbach Alpha Coefficients (on the diagonal) and Correlations of model's variables

Variable	Mean	S.D.	Correlations								
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
1. Classical Aesthetics	4.43	1.36	.90								
2. Expressive Aesthetics	3.52	1.51	.69**	.94							
3. Pleasure	3.68	1.40	.63**	.67**	.92						
4. Arousal_N	2.68	1.35	-.32**	-.24**	-.15*	.87					
5. Arousal_P	2.58	1.28	.19	.46**	.45**	.00	.82				
6. Dominance	5.24	1.26	.10	.02	-.11	-.36**	-.15*	.81			
7. Usability	4.45	1.44	.35**	.32**	.30**	-.25**	.20**	.51**	.91		
8. Attitude	3.47	1.64	.47**	.55**	.54**	-.36**	.40**	.24**	.68*	.93	

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < .01$

Note: All scales are measured on a 1 (low) to 7 (high) scale.

The correlations table indicates moderate relationships between the aesthetics variables and usability, thus partially supporting H7. To test the rest of the research hypotheses we conducted multiple regression analyses. We first regressed each of the emotional states variables on all of the environmental variables (Usability and Classical and Expressive Aesthetics). In the second stage we regressed Attitudes on all of the emotional states variables (Pleasure, Dominance, and Negative and Positive Arousal). The regression analyses allowed to examine both if the hypothesized relationships between variables in the model indeed exist

and whether there are relationships which exist despite not being hypothesized. The results are shown in Table 2 and Figure 3.

In general, the data supported the relationships posited by the model. All of the research hypotheses were supported with the exception of lack of significant impact of the site's usability on pleasure (H4). It is interesting to note that higher levels of classical aesthetics were associated with lower levels of both positive and negative arousal. Finally, approach/avoidance reactions in the context of this study were predominantly influenced by feelings of pleasure and dominance and less by arousal.

Table 2: Results of regression tests. Each test reports dependent variable first, followed by the list of independent variables

Regression tests	β	Hypothesis
1. Pleasure (<i>Adj. R</i> ² = 0.50)		
Classical aesthetics	0.31**	H1: supported
Expressive aesthetics	0.44**	H2: supported
Usability	0.04	H6: not supported
2. Arousal positive (<i>Adj. R</i> ² = 0.23)		
Classical aesthetics	-0.26*	H4: supported
Expressive aesthetics	0.60**	H3: supported
Usability	0.10	
3. Arousal negative (<i>Adj. R</i> ² = 0.11)		
Classical aesthetics	-0.27*	H4: supported
Expressive aesthetics	0.00	
Usability	-0.15	
4. Dominance (<i>Adj. R</i> ² = 0.27)		
Classical aesthetics	0.02	
Expressive aesthetics	-0.17	
Usability	0.56**	H5: supported
5. Approach attitudes (<i>R</i> ² = 0.51)		
Pleasure	0.40**	H8: supported
Arousal negative	-0.18**	
Arousal positive	0.24**	
Dominance	0.35**	H9: supported

** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 3: Model of the impact of e-store atmospherics on customer emotions and attitudes. Only significant regression coefficients are shown.

5. Conclusion

This model and the findings augment existing characterizations of the designed virtual shopping environments in several respects. Firstly, the model offers a systematic and theoretically driven treatment of e-store atmospherics and its relationship to HCI design elements. Then, it shows how these atmospherics elements affect e-shoppers' emotions, which in turn influence approach/avoidance responses (conceptualized here as attitudes towards the Web-store). Related contributions are the systematic introduction of perceived aesthetics into the study of online retail environments and the inclusion of all three aspects of the original PAD model's affective states, as opposed to recent tendencies in the marketing literature to ignore the Dominance aspect. The results indicate that feeling of dominance are strongly related to perceptions of the site's usability and to attitudes towards the store. Thus, at least in the e-retail context, dominance appears to be a viable and pertinent emotion. Finally, the results indicate that among the PAD dimensions, pleasure plays the major role in determining users' attitudes towards Web-based stores.

The major empirical deviation from the proposed model was the bi-dimensionality of the arousal construct. While this problem has been noted in previous research (e.g., Donovan et al., 1994), this issue should be addressed by future research, using a more confirmatory approach. Still, it is interesting to note that despite splitting the arousal construct into two, the hypothesized relation between the environmental variables and arousal were supported. That

is, classical aesthetics was associated with reduces levels of arousal – both positive and negative.

This is an exploratory study, and as such, it has several limitations. The results are based on a relatively small sample. This had precluded the use of more powerful statistical techniques to test the research model. It also limits the generalizability of the results. In addition, the results may reflect the nature of the stores that were used in this study. Thus, additional tests of the model with different sets of domains and stores, using larger and different samples, are required.

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Appendix 1

Pattern Matrix of the model's variables

Items	Factors							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
CA1	.787							
CA2	.593							
CA3	.666							
CA4	.771							
EA1		.663						
EA2		.836						
EA3		.789						
EA4		.876						
US1			-.636					
US2			-.749					
US3			-.911					
US4			-.672					
PL1				.749				
PL2				.859				
PL3				.862				
PL4				.612				
PL5				.560				
ARN1					.802			
ARN2					.885			
ARN3					.678			
ARN4					.765			
ARP1						.680		
ARP2						.757		
ARP3						.851		
DM1							.925	
DM2							.721	
DM3							.471	
AT1								-.671
AT2								-.817
AT3								-.728
AT4								-.740

Note: Loadings under 0.4 are not displayed.

Legend: CA = perceived classical aesthetics; EA = perceived expressive aesthetics; US = perceived usability; PL = pleasure; ARN = negative arousal; ARP = positive arousal; DM = dominance; AT = Attitude (approach/avoidance) towards the site.